

Apparent N recovery, N uptake, and yield of rice under integrated N management. Killikulam, India, 1988–89.

Treatment ^a	1988 pishanam			1989 kar			1989 pishanam		
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Total N uptake (kg/ha)	Apparent N recovery (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Total N uptake (kg/ha)	Apparent N recovery (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Total N uptake (kg/ha)	Apparent N recovery (%)
T1 - control	1.4	33		4.0	96		3.0	76	—
100 kg N/ha as									
T2 - urea	3.1	87	54	5.3	148	52	5.5	137	61
T3 - FYM	1.9	49	16	4.7	141	45	5.3	140	64
T4 - <i>Sesbania aculeata</i>	3.3	81	48	4.8	132	36	5.7	156	80
T5 - azolla	2.1	58	25	5.1	124	28	5.7	143	67
T6 - <i>Crotalaria juncea</i>	^b	^b	^b	4.5	120	24	5.3	146	70
50 kg N/ha as urea + 50 kg N/ha as									
T7 - FYM	2.7	76	43	4.8	124	28	5.7	143	67
T8 - <i>S. aculeata</i>	3.1	82	49	4.7	148	52	4.8	141	65
T9 - azolla	3.1	83	50	4.6	112	16	5.9	154	78
T10 - <i>C. juncea</i>	^b	^b	^b	7.3	142	46	5.3	145	69
1/3 N/ha each as									
T11 - <i>S. aculeata</i> + azolla + urea	3.3	94	61	4.4	108	12	5.5	128	52
T12 - <i>C. juncea</i> + azolla + urea	^b	^b	^b	4.8	108	12	6.3	151	75
T13 - <i>C. juncea</i> + urea + <i>Azospirillum</i>	^b	^b	^b	5.1	128	32	5.3	149	73
LSD (0.05)	0.2	20	22	0.55	22	21	0.4	11	11

^aTo supply 100 kg N/ha, 25 t *S. aculeata* or *C. juncea* was applied 15 d before transplanting (DBT), 20 t FYM and 25 t azolla were applied 1 DBT. Urea was applied in 3 splits: 50% basal + 25% each at tillering (30 d after transplanting [DT] and panicle initiation stage [60 DTI]). *Azospirillum* was applied as seedling dip and main field soil application. ^bTreatments not tried during 1988 pishanam.

Sep) and 1989 pishanam. Treatments were a complete N dose (100 kg N/ha) either in full or in combination with organic sources and fertilizer N (see table).

The N content of the organic sources used on a dry weight basis were 0.5% for farmyard manure (FYM), 3.2% for *Sesbania aculeata*, and 4.0% for azolla during 1988 pishanam and 0.5% for FYM, 3.3% for *S. aculeata*, 3.4% for *Crotalaria juncea*, and 4.0% for azolla during 1989 kar. Organic N sources were not applied during 1989 pishanam, but the full N dose was applied as prilled urea in three splits.

S. aculeata applied alone or in combination with azolla and urea gave yields similar to those from a full dose of urea N in 1988 pishanam. N applied 50% through *C. juncea* and 50% through urea produced 37% higher yields than a full dose applied as urea during 1989 kar. Applying a full N dose as *C. juncea* + azolla + urea during 1989 pishanam recorded 15% higher yield than a full dose of urea N.

In 1989 pishanam and kar, substituting *S. aculeata* for the N requirement, either fully or at half level, recorded a N recovery equal to application of a full dose of N as urea. □

Grain yields of rainfed rice - lentil as affected by N fertilizer and biofertilizer

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We evaluated the relative efficiency of biofertilizers *Sesbania rostrata*, *S. aculeata*, and *Corchorus olitorius* L. and N levels (0, 50, and 100 kg/ha) from urea on grain yield of transplanted rainfed rice during the 1990 summer and wet seasons and of residual lentil during 1990–91 winter in WB.

Soil was clayey loam with 0.61% organic C, 0.062% total N, 15 kg available P, 160 kg available K/ha, and pH 6.8.

Seeds of green manure crops *S. rostrata* and *S. aculeata* were broadcast on 7 May 1990 at 30 kg seed/ha and of leaf manure crop *C. olitorius* (cultivar Basudev) at 7 kg seed/ha in a split-plot design with four

replications. The control was left fallow. Green and leaf manures were incorporated in a 7- × 5-m plot on 17 Jul.

On 8 Aug, 30-d-old IR36 rice seedlings were transplanted in subplots with 4 seedlings/hill at 25- × 10-cm spacing. We applied 20 kg/ha each of P and K and half of each N treatment. The other half was applied 30 d after transplanting. Rice was harvested 4 Nov.

Lentil (*Lens culinaris* L. cultivar B77) seeds at 15 kg/ha were broadcast over the standing rice one day before it was

harvested. Lentil was harvested 10 Feb.

Rice grain yields with green manure from *S. rostrata* or *S. aculeata* were significantly higher than those with either leaf manure from *C. olitorius* or the control.

Rice yields increased significantly as N levels increased. Rice yields with *S. rostrata* and *S. aculeata* increased equally with both 50 and 100 kg N/ha. Neither biofertilizer nor N level significantly affected lentil grain yield (see table). □

Effect of N fertilizer and biofertilizer on grain yield of transplanted rainfed rice and the aftereffects on lentil. West Bengal, India, 1990–91.

Treatment	Rice and lentil grain yields (t/ha)					
	No N		50 kg N/ha		100 kg N/ha	
	Rice	Lentil	Rice	Lentil	Rice	Lentil
Fallow (control)	2.1	1.1	3.2	1.0	3.5	0.7
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i>	3.2	1.2	3.1	0.6	4.9	0.4
<i>Sesbania rostrata</i>	3.2	0.6	4.0	0.8	4.4	1.0
<i>Corchorus olitorius</i>	2.5	1.1	2.7	0.7	3.4	0.9
LSD (0.05)	0.7	ns	0.4	ns	0.8	ns